

Frameworks and methods for estimating causal effect of clinical treatment in orthopaedics: A scoping review protocol

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Abstract

Introduction: The gold standard for establishing the causal effect of a clinical treatment is a randomized controlled trial (RCT), which is challenging to apply in orthopaedics, mainly due to ethical reasons. Therefore, retrospective observational studies were conducted to elucidate potential treatment effects. Unfortunately, causal inference has remained largely underutilized in neuro-orthopaedics and gait analysis. Many causal inference methodologies worthy of consideration may have been utilized in orthopaedics, where RCTs are difficult to implement. The objective of the scoping review is to facilitate a better understanding of the use of causal inference methods in orthopaedics.

Methods and analysis: The scoping review adheres to the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology and five-stage Arksey and O'Malley's framework. Two themes, "orthopaedic interventions" and "causal inference", guide the search strategy development for this scoping review. A literature search of observational studies will be conducted using the PubMed, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, EMBASE, and SCOPUS databases. Studies that describe the use of causal inference frameworks in the setting of clinical treatment in orthopaedics will be included. Two independent reviewers will conduct the study screening and assessment of the full texts. The charting of the Data for the included studies will follow the JBI template for data extraction.

Ethics and dissemination: This scoping review does not require any ethical approval. We will only use data from publicly available literature. Our dissemination strategy includes open-access publications in peer-reviewed journals.

Protocol summary

Strengths and limitations of the planned study

- The proposed scoping review maps the use of causal inference frameworks and methods in clinical treatment in orthopaedics.
- This scoping review is expected to assess the current state of methods for estimating the causal effects of clinical treatments in orthopaedics from observational studies.
- The review process is guided by the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews.

The quality of the evidence will be evaluated using the Cochrane's Risk of Bias in Non-Randomized Studies - of Interventions (ROBINS-I) tool.

Keywords: Propensity Score, Orthopaedic Procedures, Gait Analysis

Introduction

Orthopaedics, also known as orthopaedic surgery, is a medical specialty that focuses on the diagnosis, treatment, prevention, and rehabilitation of conditions and injuries related to the musculoskeletal system. The musculoskeletal system includes bones, joints, ligaments, tendons, muscles, and nerves that allow the body to move and function properly. Treatments to address a musculoskeletal problem may or may not include surgical techniques to treat conditions such as fractures, dislocations, sprains, strains, arthritis, deformities, tumors, sports injuries, and other disorders affecting the bones, joints, muscles, and supporting structures.

The gold standard to establish the causal effect of a clinical treatment is a randomized controlled trial (RCT), which may be difficult to implement in orthopaedics for practical and ethical reasons. Malavolta et al. (2011) [1] described several difficulties in conducting RCTs in the field of orthopaedics; fundamental steps, such as patient selection, randomization, and blinding, raise challenges when surgical procedures are involved. First, recruitment is often difficult, because patients may have a strong preference for surgical treatment. New and experimental surgical procedures can cause

patients to be anxious and apprehensive to a greater extent compared to new medication, knowing that surgery is often permanent and there is no washout period, which allows the treatment to be completely eliminated from the patient's system, as can be found with the application of medications. Second, randomization is particularly difficult because the surgical techniques must be randomized. Any limitation to carrying out one of the surgeries (only certain days, specific surgeon, etc.) can harm this principle. For example, complex emergency or trauma surgery may be subject to the availability of surgeons with a certain skill set, which would impair randomization. Other difficulties may arise in studies involving comparisons between different implants. In an ideal situation, the assignment to treatment groups should be made at the time of the surgery, but often preparation for the procedure needs to be planned and the team needs to be prepared, which can cause loss of blinding. Another problem is that inclusion for surgery can only be defined after intraoperative evaluation, for example, suturing a meniscal tear. In such cases, intraoperative randomization must be performed. In studies involving nonsurgical groups, blinding of the surgeon is not possible. Furthermore, when required by the RCT, the use of placebo surgery has serious ethical concerns. In studies comparing two surgical interventions, if the operative techniques differ, blinding of the surgeon is impossible, and bias could be induced if the surgeon believes more in one technique and makes greater efforts towards it. Blinding of patients is compromised when different access routes are used. If different treatments used different implants, the patient could also notice differences between implants if the patient had access to radiographic examination. Blinding of independent assessors, typically physicians or physiotherapists, may be lost when different techniques use different access routes, leading to different scars. Blinding may also be lost when different surgical interventions require different types of rehabilitation. In summary, many factors impede the feasibility of conducting RCTs in orthopaedics. In the absence of RCTs, observational studies may provide useful evidence to compare different treatments. When using observational data to estimate the effects of individual interventions, it is beneficial to frame studies in a formal causal inference framework to enhance transparency and quality [2].

Causal inference is the process of determining cause-effect relationships between variables based on evidence, observations, and reasoning. Causal inference frameworks may incorporate potential outcomes, counterfactual reasoning, and causal graphs to describe cause-effect relationships, as well as statistical methods for estimating identifiable effects [3].

Neuro-orthopaedics is a sub-field of orthopaedics primarily concerned with addressing musculoskeletal deformities secondary to disorders affecting motor control. Within neuro-orthopaedics, clinical gait analysis (CGA) is used to inform the decision-making process. Baker et al. (2009) defined CGA as 'the process of determining what is causing patients to walk the way they do'

[4]. Unlike most orthopaedic sub-fields, CGA provides a very rich dataset, including kinematics and kinetics of the lower limb joints during walking, to document the patient's motor function pre- and post-treatment. There are well-established outcome measures based on CGA to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions aimed at improving the walking function. For example, the gait profile score provides an accurate assessment of deviations from normal gait, including their extent and location [5] [6], while the gait standard deviation [7] measures the variability in the gait pattern, which varies based on primary motor disorders. Therefore, many major neuro-orthopaedic centers routinely collect gait analysis data to guide surgical decisions and evaluate treatment outcomes.

Research gap

Causal inference has demonstrated promise in evaluating the impact of treatment by showing consistency with results from RCTs targeting the same estimand [8]. Numerous methodologies that warrant consideration may have been utilized in orthopaedics, where RCTs are difficult to implement. A scoping review is required to obtain a comprehensive overview of the use, benefits, and limitations of causal inference methods in orthopaedics. Furthermore, we aim to review if and how rich datasets provided by CGA may facilitate causal inference methods in orthopaedics.

Methods

Protocol design

The review process is guided by the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) methodology for scoping reviews [9]. This scoping review draws inspiration from Arksey and O'Malley's five-stage approach: (1) identifying the research question; (2) identifying relevant studies; (3) study selection; (4) charting the data; and (5) collating, summarizing, and reporting the results [10].

Stage 1: identifying the research question

This study aims to assess the current state of methods for estimating the causal effects of clinical treatments in orthopaedics from observational studies. The main research question focuses on mapping practices in terms of frameworks and methods to address the causal inference of clinical treatments in orthopaedics. The scoping review will be guided by the following key questions.

1. What causal inference frameworks have been proposed to assess the effect of clinical treatment in orthopaedics?
2. What was the origin of the data used for the assessment:

- research or clinical data,
- size of the data,
- monocentric or multicentric settings?

3. Which interventions and outcomes were investigated?

Stage 2: identifying relevant studies

To identify relevant studies, we will use the Population, Concept and Context (PCC) approach to determine which studies are eligible for the scoping review (see Table 1). The search strategy will be defined according to these eligibility criteria. To be included, studies must have full text available. No restrictions on the dates will be applied. The search strategy will consist of free text and, where applicable, MeSH terms (see Table 3). The search terms will be developed using the method described by Hausner et al. (2012) [11]. For each PCC element, we iterate the following process: we aim to generate a set of studies that are relevant to one PCC element and use it to develop a search strategy for this PCC element. To do so, we select references from scoping and systematic reviews that include the same PCC element. This forms the basis of a set of relevant studies. We then analyzed the term frequency to identify relevant terms from the titles and abstracts of the set of studies. We then assemble these terms into a search strategy that best represents the set of studies.

A literature search of studies will be conducted in the PubMed, Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, EMBASE, and SCOPUS databases. The initial database to search will be PubMed, and the search string will subsequently be adapted for other databases. Once all search strings are developed, they will be re-run concurrently on the same day, and the final results are further processed. The search will be performed between November 2023 and January 2023. When all the articles are screened, references can be added through reference chasing or personal libraries.

Table 1: Population, concept, context (PCC) framework and types of evidence for identifying the main concepts within the research question.

PCC Element	Inclusion	Exclusion
Population	Human patients subject to an orthopaedic clinical treatment, which can be orthopaedic surgery, conservative treatment with orthotics, physiotherapy, or occupational therapy.	Animals
Concept	Studies that describe the use of a causal inference framework to assess effects of an orthopaedic treatment.	Studies estimating a causal effect using RCT only

Context	Any geographical location or setting of any nature	None
Types of evidence	Observational studies (eg, cohort studies and case-control studies in which intervention groups are allocated during the course of usual treatment decisions, and quasi-randomised studies in which the method of allocation falls short of full randomisation), Full-text articles	Reviews (eg, systematic reviews, narrative reviews)

Stage 3: study selection

We will extract studies using the Rayyan web application for systematic reviews [12]. A web application will be used for data management and screening. After removing duplicates, two independent reviewers will individually screen all titles and abstracts to select studies related to our Population, Concept and Context, as described above. The second stage includes a full-text screening. This will be done by two independent reviewers selecting studies that align with our predefined inclusion criteria. Studies that potentially meet the inclusion criteria will be retrieved from the full text during this screening stage. Full-text studies failing to meet the inclusion criteria will be excluded, and justifications for exclusion will be provided in the final report. The results of the search will be reported in full in the final report and presented as a PRISMA flow diagram. Disagreements emerging among the reviewers will be resolved through discussion or by involving a third reviewer (i.e., a co-author). First, both reviewers will screen a certain percentage of the studies before meeting and evaluate their shared comprehension of the PCC inclusion/exclusion criteria. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion until consensus is reached. A third evaluator will be sought in the absence of consensus. If a study has been published multiple times, the most recent publication will be retained.

Stage 4: charting the data

A charting table adopted from Joanna Briggs Institute's template for data extraction [9] was used to record the key information of the source (see Table 2). This may be further refined at the review stage, and the charting table updated accordingly. To ensure the validity of the process, the form will be piloted and tested against a few studies and discussed with all the coauthors. Two independent reviewers will extract the data, and disagreements will be resolved by consensus among team

members. Quality assessment of the studies will be performed using the Cochrane’s Risk of Bias in Non-randomized Studies - of Interventions (ROBINS-I) tool [13].

Table 2: Charting table following the Joanna Briggs Institute’s template for data extraction.

Dimensions	Details
Citation details	Author/s, Year of publication, Title, Country
Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria	Population, Concept, Context, Types of evidence source
Evidence source Details and Characteristics	Aims/purpose, Participants (details e.g. age/sex and number), Intervention type, Comparator and details of these (e.g. duration of the intervention), Outcomes and details of these (e.g. how measured)
Details/Results extracted from source of evidence	Causal inference methods used, Use of target trial, Use of causal graphs, Centre type (unicentric or multicentric)

Stage 5: collating, summarizing, and reporting the results.

From the included literature, we will provide an overview of the causal inference methods used to evaluate the effectiveness of clinical treatment in orthopaedics. We will put these frameworks in relation to the use of target trials, center type, use of causal graphs, or year of publication. A descriptive analysis will be performed. Finally, a summary of the findings will be described through narrative synthesis.

Ethics and dissemination

Approval from the Human Research Ethics Committee was not required. This study is a scoping review of the published literature and involved neither human participants nor unpublished secondary data. The findings of the scoping review will be disseminated through open-access publications in peer-reviewed journals.

Footnotes

Author contributions: BW developed the scoping review protocol and search strategy and wrote the first version of the manuscript. MK, MSa, MSi, and GM contributed to drafting the scoping review protocol. GM provided expertise in causal inferences. EV and MSa provided expertise in orthopaedics. All authors reviewed the final approved protocol.

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Data sharing statement: The manuscript is a protocol for scoping reviews. Therefore, we currently do not have any data.

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Appendix

Table 3: Pubmed search string

	Stream (Pubmed)
A	("orthopedic procedures"[MeSH Terms]) OR (("orthopaedic"[Title/Abstract] OR "orthopedic"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("surger"[Title/Abstract] OR "surgical"[Title/Abstract] OR "intervention"[Title/Abstract] OR "procedure"[Title/Abstract]))
B	("causal effect"[Title/Abstract] OR "causal inference"[Title/Abstract] OR "Propensity Score"[MeSH Terms] OR "propensity score"[Title/Abstract] OR "instrumental var"[Title/Abstract] OR "directed acyclic graph"[Title/Abstract] OR "inverse probability weighting"[Title/Abstract] OR "trial emulation"[Title/Abstract] OR "g method"[Title/Abstract] OR "g formula"[Title/Abstract] OR "g computation"[Title/Abstract])
Combination	((("orthopedic procedures"[MeSH Terms]) OR (("orthopaedic"[Title/Abstract] OR "orthopedic"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("surger"[Title/Abstract] OR "surgical"[Title/Abstract] OR "intervention"[Title/Abstract] OR "procedure"[Title/Abstract]))) AND ("Causal Effect"[Title/Abstract] OR "Causal Inference"[Title/Abstract] OR "Propensity Score"[MeSH Terms] OR "propensity score"[Title/Abstract] OR "instrumental var"[Title/Abstract] OR "directed acyclic graph"[Title/Abstract] OR "inverse probability weighting"[Title/Abstract] OR "trial emulation"[Title/Abstract] OR "g-method"[Title/Abstract] OR "g-formula"[Title/Abstract] OR "g-computation"[Title/Abstract])